

Spectrophotometric determination of Metoprolol tartrate in bulk drug and tablets

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Abstract: A simple and cost effective spectrophotometric method is described for the determination of metoprolol tartrate in bulk drug and tablets. This method is based on the secondary amino groups. The reaction between metoprolol tartrate and metal is a simple condensation reaction with carbon disulphide in the presence of ammonia to form the corresponding dithiocarbamate, which forms a colored complex with metal ions. The colored species has an absorption maximum at 435 nm and obey Beer's law in the concentration range 30–300 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{ml}^{-1}$. Results of analysis were validated statistically and by recovery studies. The method was found to be suitable for routine determination of metoprolol tartrate.

Keywords: Metoprolol, spectrophotometric, colorimetric, β -blockers.

Introduction

Metoprolol tartrate (MT) is chemically (*RS*)-1-isopropylamine-3-*p*-(2-methoxyethyl)phenoxypropan-2-ol(2*R*,3*R*)-tartrate (Fig. 1). It is a cardio-selective β -blocking agent with intrinsic sympathomimetic activity which slows the heart rate^{1,2}. It is one of the potent drugs as its small quantity is enough to aggravate the desired pharmacological action³. MT is prepared by chemical synthesis and the racemate is used clinically⁴. MT is administered orally or intravenously⁵. The therapeutic importance of this drug has prompted the development of many methods for its

Fig. 1. Structure of Metoprolol tartrate.

assay. The literature survey revealed titrimetric and spectrophotometric methods^{6–9}. In addition, several methods have been reported for quantification of metoprolol in plasma using high-performance liquid chromatography with UV or fluorescence detection^{10–17}. Colorimetric determination of some β -blocking drugs has been reported^{18–25}. The purpose of this investigation was to develop a simple and sensitive visible spectrophotometric method for the quantitation of MT in pure drug and in pharmaceutical formulations. This method uses the well known condensation reaction involving copper metal and results in the formation of a yellow color chromogen that could be measured at 435 nm.

Results and discussion

This method is based on the secondary amino groups. The reaction between MT and metal is a simple condensation reaction with CS_2 in the presence of ammonia to form the corresponding dithiocarbamate, which forms a colored complex with metal ions (Fig. 2).

In the present work a colorimetric method has

Fig. 2. Formation of metal-dithiocarbamate complex.

been developed for the estimation of MT in bulk and tablet dosage forms. The yellow colored chromogen formed shows absorption maxima at 435 nm (Fig. 3). Beer's law was followed in the concentration range of 30–300 mg/mL. Regression equation was found to be $y = 0.003x + 0.021$ and coefficient of correlation was 0.998 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Scan of Metoprolol tartrate complex.

Fig. 4. Calibration curve of Metoprolol tartrate complex with cupric acetate at 435 nm.

The molar absorptivity values (high) and Sandell's sensitivity values (low) show that method is sensitive. The results of analysis of bulk and commercial formulations significantly showed low values of standard deviation, standard error of the mean, coefficient of variation and percent range of error (within 95% confidence limits) and thus show precision of the method.

Experimental

Instrumentation:

UV-1800 UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan, equipped with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used in the present investigation. A Citizen scale, Japan analytical balance was used.

Materials and reagent:

Drug procured from IPCA Laboratories Limited, Sajavata, Ratlam, Madhya Pradesh, Regd. off. 48, Kandivali Ind. Estate, Mumbai. All the chemicals used during the experiment were of analytical grade.

Preparation of metal solution (0.0025% w/v): Cupric acetate (250 mg) dissolved in 100 mL methanol to give the required solution.

Preparation of ammonia solution: 25% (v/v) solution prepared in ethanol.

Preparation of carbon disulphide (CS₂) solution: 10% (v/v) solutions prepared in ethanol.

Preparation of stock solution (S): A solution of metoprolol tartrate was prepared by dissolving 100 mg (accurately weighed) of drug in ethanol in 100 mL volumetric flask (1000 mg/mL).

Steps of method development:

Preliminary trials were made for the study of this method to see and fix the various parameters that should be chosen for the successful estimation of this drug. These parameters govern the accuracy and sensitivity of the method and need to be optimized. On the basis of these parameters the work was divided into following heads:

(i) Development of color and determination of absorption maxima, (ii) Stability studies of colored chromogen, (iii) Plotting of calibration curve, (iv)

Optical characteristics, (v) Estimation from bulk, its statistical analysis and validation, (vi) Recovery studies in bulk, (vii) Estimation of formulations (tablet), its statistical analysis and validation, (viii) Recovery studies of formulations (tablet).

Development of color and determination of absorption maxima:

The dilutions 30 to 300 µg/mL drug solutions (2 mL) were transferred to test tubes and 1 mL carbon disulphide solution, 0.5 mL ammonia solution were added in each test tube. All of the test tubes were vortexed for 2 min and then 1 mL metal solution was added to each. The yellow colored chromogen was developed. This was then scanned in visible range. This showed absorption maxima at 435 nm.

Stability studies of colored chromogen:

The absorbance of the above solution was read at 435 nm periodically at every 30 min up to 120 min. The yellow colored chromogen was remaining stable up to 3 h.

Plotting of calibration curve:

Aliquots of (30 to 300 µg/mL) concentrations were taken and above procedure was followed to draw the calibration curve.

Optical characteristics:

The optical characteristics such as absorption maxima, Beer's law limit, correlation coefficient (*r*), slope (*m*), intercept (*c*), molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity were calculated and the results are shown in Table 1.

Molar absorption coefficient (molar absorptivity) (ϵ) is defined as the absorbance of 1 molar solution in a cell of 1 cm path length, which is given by:

$$\epsilon = A/cl$$

Parameters	Values
Absorption maxima	435 nm
Beer's law limit	30–300 µg/mL
Molar absorptivity	992.776 L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Sandell's sensitivity	0.26930 µg cm ⁻² / 0.001 Absorbance unit
Regression equation	y = 0.003x + 0.021
Slope	0.003 (<i>m</i>)
Intercept	0.021 (<i>c</i>)
Correlation coefficient	0.998

Molar absorption coefficient (ϵ) = $E^{1\%}_{1\text{cm}} \times \text{molecular weight}/10$

The sensitivity of the methods was adjudged by Sandell's sensitivity. It can be defined as the smallest weight of substance that can be detected in column of solution of unit cross section. The weight of sample can be conveniently expressed in µg and area in cm.

Sandell's sensitivity (*S*) values were determined from molar absorptivity using relationship:

$$S = \text{Molecular weight}/\text{Molar absorptivity} = M/\epsilon$$

Estimation from bulk drug:

Stock solution was prepared by dissolving 100 mg (accurately weighed) of standard MT in 100 mL of ethanol. Aliquots of a definite concentration were further suitably diluted to give the concentration in the range of calibration curve. The drug content was calculated and the experiments were repeated six times to check its reproducibility (Table 2).

Recovery studies in bulk drug:

Recovery studies were performed by standard

Table 2. Compilation of statistical analysis in case of bulk drug (Metoprolol tartrate)

Sl. No.	Concentration taken (µg/mL) ^a	Concentration found (µg/mL) ^a	S.D. ^a	C.V.*	S.E. ^a	<i>t</i> Calculated ^a	<i>t</i> Theoretical
1.	200.00	200.88	2.248	1.119	0.9176	0.9687	3.365
2.	300.00	299.388	0.772	0.258	0.315	1.938	

*Average of six determinations.

S.D.: Standard deviation. C.V.: Coefficient of variation. S.E.: Standard error of mean.

addition method. Pure drug was added to the previously analyzed pharmaceutical drug and the mixtures were analyzed by the proposed method in six replicates in six volumetric flasks (10 mL). Here 10 mg of pure drug was added to the 100 mg of accurately weighed MT. Data are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Complication of results of drug recovery studies

Sl. No.	Concentration proposed ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) ^a	% Recovery \pm S.D.
1.	220	99.646 \pm 1.186
2.	330	99.832 \pm 1.089

*Average of six determinations.

S.D.: Standard deviation.

Estimation from tablets:

The tablet formulations of MT were procured from the local market and average weight was determined (Table 4). The tablets of each composition of formulation were powdered separately. The powdered tablets (powder equivalent to 100 mg) were taken in 100 mL of volumetric flask separately. These were

Table 4. Average weights of tablets

Tablet	Drug content (mg)	Average weight of uncoated tablets (g)
Betaloc 100 (Astrazenica)	100	0.3120
Embata 100 (Intas)	100	0.3592

Table 5. Compilation of result of statistical analysis of commercial formulations of Metoprolol tartrate

Sl. No.	Brand	Amt. proposed (mg/tab.)	Amt. found ^a (mg/tab.)	S.D. ^a	C.V. ^a	S.E. ^a	<i>t</i> Calculated ^a	<i>t</i> Theoretical ^a
1.	Betaloc 100	100	98.97	0.370	0.374	0.151	6.803	6.869
2.	Embata 100	100	99.12	0.594	0.599	0.242	3.627	

*Average of six determinations.

S.D.: Standard deviation. C.V.: Coefficient of variation. S.E.: Standard error.

Theoretical '*t*' values are calculated as 95% confidence level for (n-1) degree of freedom '*t*' (0.0005) = 6.869.

Table 6. Complication of results of drug recovery studies

Sl. No.	Brand	Amount proposed (mg/tab.)	% Recovery \pm S.D.
1.	Betaloc 100	100	99.57 \pm 0.210
2.	Embata 100	100	99.57 \pm 0.240

*Average of six determinations.

S.D.: Standard deviation.

extracted with ethanol (4 \times 20 mL), filtered in 100 mL volumetric flask and the volumes were made up. Aliquots of a definite concentration were further suitably diluted to give the concentration in the range. The drug content in the tablet was calculated. The experiments were repeated six times to check its reproducibility (Table 5).

Recovery studies of formulations (tablet):

Recovery studies were performed by standard addition method. Pure drug was added to the previously analyzed pharmaceutical preparation and the mixtures were analyzed by the proposed method in six replicates in six volumetric flasks (10 mL). Here 10 mg of pure drug was added to the tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg of MT (Table 6).

Conclusion

The reproducibility, repeatability, and accuracy of this method were found to be good, which is evident by low standard deviation values. The percent recovery experiment values obtained indicates non-interference from the excipients used in the formulations. The percentage recovery was close to 100% for these methods. Thus, it can be concluded that the method developed was simple, accurate, sensitive and precise. Hence, these can be successfully applied in the estimation of Metoprolol tartrate. It can

be readily adopted for routine control analysis of the drug in its formulations.

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